

**PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS IN LAYING ENGINEERING SYSTEMS
WITH MODERN MATERIALS AND EQUIPMENT**

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Abstract: Today, the issue of high-quality, reliable and energy-efficient organization of engineering systems in the construction industry is becoming increasingly relevant. Engineering networks - namely, heating, cooling, water supply, sewage, power supply and ventilation systems - are one of the main factors determining the functional efficiency of buildings. The use of modern materials and innovative equipment ensures long-term, safe and economically profitable operation of these systems. At the same time, a number of technical, economic and organizational problems are encountered in their implementation. This article analyzes the existing technical, organizational and economic problems in the process of laying engineering systems based on modern materials and equipment. Also, effective solutions are proposed for the introduction of innovative technologies in the field, increasing energy efficiency and ensuring system reliability.

Keywords: engineering systems, modern materials, energy efficiency, automation, heat supply, water supply, digital technologies. hydromechanical equipment, device, water transmission, pipeline.

Introduction: Engineering systems are the "lifblood" of any structure. Through them, vital processes such as heat, water, electricity and air exchange are controlled. The reliability of the system determines the quality of construction, the

level of safety and comfortable living conditions. [3] In our independent Republic of Uzbekistan, in order to further increase the well-being of society, improve the living conditions of people, provide them with separate housing, improve the state of engineering communications, provide clean drinking water, and develop sewage networks, our government has issued and implemented resolutions, laws and orders on them. [1] In recent years, traditional steel, copper and concrete materials have been replaced by polymer, composite and energy-saving materials. These materials not only increase the quality of systems, but also ensure their environmental safety. [12]

For example:

Polypropylene (PP-R) pipes - corrosion-resistant, easy to install and have a long service life;

Metal-plastic pipes - are distinguished by their elasticity and heat resistance;

Thermal insulation panels - reduce heat loss;

Intelligent sensors - allow automatic detection of system malfunctions.

In modern construction processes, engineering systems (heating, ventilation, water supply, sewage, power supply and telecommunications systems) play an important role in ensuring the functional operation of the building and a comfortable environment for users. In recent years, global trends have been directed towards the use of energy-efficient, environmentally friendly and long-lasting materials. Therefore, the issue of laying engineering systems with modern materials and equipment has become a problem of not only technical, but also economic and environmental importance. [13]

The main requirements for engineering networks today are:

ensuring energy efficiency and economy of systems;

reducing maintenance costs throughout their service life;

increasing the simplicity and safety of the installation process;

environmental sustainability and reducing waste;

introducing automated control and monitoring systems.

These requirements can only be met through the use of advanced technologies and modern composite, polymer and metal-plastic materials.

After gaining independence, our government paid great attention to the issue of providing the population with clean and high-quality drinking water. In particular, new networks were built and pipelines were reconstructed. As a result, the centralized drinking water supply of about 5.5 million people living in more than 1,600 villages and settlements was improved. Currently, more than 200 cities, district centers, urban-type settlements, and about 9 thousand villages and settlements are provided with drinking water. In particular, taking into account the uneven location of water sources, the limited supply and quality of their reserves, the climate, and the peculiarities of people's lifestyles, a unique drinking water supply system has been created. [11]

In all regions of our country, in the above-mentioned villages, in order to provide clean drinking water to the population living in small-sized new-type model residential buildings, we will mention water disinfection: These small-sized new-type model residential buildings use groundwater for drinking and household purposes, and water is pumped to the disinfection building. It is disinfected using chlorination equipment, which is widely used in water disinfection. [2]

Ultraviolet equipment is a complex electrical equipment. The prices of ultraviolet equipment depend on the quality of their lamps, equipment, and the automation of the equipment. The main part of ultraviolet equipment consists of a camera and a radiation zone, a starting device block, and a control block. The disinfection chamber is made of stainless steel, and ultraviolet lamps are placed inside the chamber. In water disinfection equipment, the lamps are placed in a quartz container, which protects the ultraviolet lamps from contact with water. The number and location of the lamps directly depend on the consumption of drinking water. [3]

Ultraviolet equipment is monitored and controlled. The control panel displays the status of the equipment, the operating hours of the lamps, and the ultraviolet sensor indicators. The control block of industrially manufactured equipment is equipped with an effective display and has a wide range of functions. The control block information can be transmitted to other automated control devices for control. The amount of doses is determined by the amount of water and the interaction of the ultraviolet rays with the environment. Ultraviolet equipment is divided into conical and modular (lattice) types. Conical devices are used in pressurized and non-pressurized systems. Modular or tray UV devices are used in non-pressurized systems. Modular UV systems consist of lamp blocks, which are installed in trays, mechanical cleaning systems mounted on modules, a control block, and water quality control in the trays. [5]

In general, the country's water supply pipeline system is outdated, which leads to a high number of accidents. The fact that the ground is overloaded with communications, stray currents, and electrolytic impurities accelerates the corrosion process of steel pipes, and an increase in temperature in itself accelerates chemical and other corrosion processes, which leads to pipe failure. [3]

Naturally, the following conclusion follows from this. To solve the problem, it is necessary to look for the replacement of worn-out pipes and equipment in the "new coordinate system". That is, the use of stainless pipes, which does not allow efforts to restore anti-corrosion coatings, diagnostics and other expensive work. From the point of view of economic efficiency, fiberglass pipes that create water pressure and sewage in construction are becoming popular. They are highly resistant to corrosion, reliable and durable (service life not less than 50 years), resistant to heat of the transported liquid (ambient temperature 130°C). Due to the smooth inner surface of the pipe, the coefficient of hydraulic resistance is small, and due to the deformability of the material, they are resistant to shock and vibration forces. The dosage of the sensor indicators is carried out taking into account the

amount of water and the effect of ultraviolet rays on the environment. Ultraviolet devices are divided into conical and modular (tray) types. Conical devices are used in pressure and non-pressure systems. Ultraviolet modular or tray devices are used in non-pressure systems. Modular ultraviolet systems consist of lamp blocks, which are installed in trays, mechanical cleaning systems installed in modules, a control block and water quality control in trays. [7]

Compared to steel pipes, with the same strength, fiberglass pipes are 4 times lighter, have a smooth inner surface, do not clog, which allows the use of pipes of smaller diameter. Compared to polymer-cored pipes, they have lower flammability (oxygen index 39), higher physical and mechanical properties, long-term durability, resistance to overloads at temperatures up to 130°C, working pressure up to 1.5 mPa. When constructing a pipeline from heat-resistant fiberglass pipes, the payback period is 1.5-2 years, excluding heat and energy consumption. Since steel pipes require replacement after 8-12 years, the return on investment of fiberglass pipes over 50 years is five times less than that of the laid pipe. [9]

The use of fiberglass pipes in water supply in our republic is also highly effective, since the transition to fiberglass pipes in water supply networks increases the service life of the network by 4 times and reduces energy consumption by 2-3 times due to the absence of internal blockages in the pipe. The current widespread use of such pipes is due to the lack of raw materials for polypropylene. The main raw material for the production of fiberglass pipes is polypropylene, which is in sufficient supply in our country. [10]

Each device must perform its intended function for a long time. Therefore, the most important thing when designing a device is to be able to choose the materials used. The fittings of drinking water devices must be resistant to slightly acidic water (pH value) for at least 6.5 years. [14]

Steel contains hard iron carbide (Fe_3C) and soft iron crystals called ferrite. The properties of steel can be changed through additional alloys. Steel pipes used

for drinking water must contain at least 16% chromium. Steel pipes with a low carbon content and containing a carbon mesh are called austenitic steel pipes. Such pipes are easily connected with manual pressing equipment. [10]

Metals and their alloys are of crucial importance in engineering, especially in gas supply and heating networks. Steel is valued for its cheapness and strength, cast iron for its durability, copper for its hygienic properties, and aluminum for its lightness. Modern technologies further extend the service life of metal pipes by protecting them with special coatings. [14]

Economical thinking does not only mean completing the work in a short time, but also choosing materials that protect the environment while taking responsibility for society. When designing drinking water installations, the possibility of recycling and the energy consumption for reusing them in the event of separation should be considered. When considering the technology for connecting plastic pipes to metal pipes for drinking water, at least 5 times more energy is consumed. [9]

They differ from thermoplastic polymers in their high strength, heat resistance and hardness. This group includes urea, phenol-formaldehyde, epoxy and some other polymers. [10] Fillers are substances added to plastics to give them the necessary properties (high strength, heat resistance, high impact resistance, high impact viscosity) and to reduce their cost. As fillers, powdery (quartz flour, chalk, talc, wood flour, etc.), fibrous (asbestos, wood and glass fibers) and layered (paper, yarn, wood, veneer, etc.) substances are used. Each filler improves one property of the plastic, but worsens another to one degree or another, therefore, when choosing and determining their quantity, it is necessary to take into account the function of the material and the conditions of its use. [11] Plasticizers improve the plastic properties of plastics and facilitate their processing. Dibutyl phthalate, camphor, oleic acid, etc. are used as plasticizers. [10] If the Ustyurt Chemical-Gas complex is put into operation, one hundred thousand tons of polypropylene will be produced per year. Such pipes are currently manufactured by the Swiss-German company

HOBAS and are being used in Russia. The use and production of such pipes in Uzbekistan is of great importance, since in the near future we plan to produce the main raw material polypropylene starting from 2015. To increase the resistance of wells of urban water supply and sewage networks, it is planned to use protective shells from groundwater and dissolved salts. The protective shell consists of cement mixtures and bitumen liquid, and the well seams are filled with cement mixture and polished. [3] When assembling polyethylene pipes used in water supply and sewage, it is necessary to produce threaded couplings, use them, and when laying water supply and sewage systems, it is necessary to produce and use polyethylene wells. [4] The scientific work of the dissertation is the production and use of flanged polyethylene pipes of various sizes and the addition of circular metal wires to the pipe wall to increase the pipe strength in the production of polyethylene pipes. [9]

Production and use of polyethylene wells in laying water supply and sewage networks. [4]

Conclusion: Laying engineering systems based on modern materials and advanced technologies not only increases the technical efficiency of structures, but also ensures energy efficiency, environmental safety and economic stability. For the development of the industry, it is necessary to implement innovative approaches, research and development, and digital technologies. This will allow the construction industry of Uzbekistan to have sustainable and competitive systems that meet global standards. In order to take measures to prevent the increase in problems with water supply and sewage systems in multi-storey residential buildings, it was ensured that construction was organized in compliance with the Code of Conduct for Construction and Installation Works. Construction and installation works were carried out using modern equipment and modern materials. An analysis of the technical condition of the water supply network pipelines shows that the pipelines are performing their functions perfectly. The main problem is that in the current conditions of increasing water resource shortage, it is of particular

importance to develop measures such as water conservation and neutralization, more economical use of water resources, search for and use of water sources that will increase water resources, and prevent the negative impact of water on the environment. Water makes up three-quarters of the Earth's surface and an average of 85 percent of the human body. These figures alone are an indication of the level of water demand in nature and humans. Currently, about 5 million people worldwide fall ill every year due to lack of clean water. In general, the number of people suffering from water-related diseases is 1.4 billion. One of the most important and integral sectors of the economy of our republic is the construction sector. Currently, the attention paid to the construction sector is very great, and a lot of work is being done in this regard. One of the important tasks is to install communication networks for all types of residential, public and other buildings being built in urban and rural areas, as well as to connect communication networks in rural areas. That is, all household and social facilities related to the comfortable life of the population are being built simultaneously.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati

[1] 2017-2021 yillarda O'zbekiston Respublikasining rivojlantirish harakatlar strategiyasining beshta ustuvor yo'nalishi to'g'risida. Qismlar-4.3- 4.4 Toshkent, 2017 yil. www.gov.uz-O'zbekiston Respublikasi xukumat portali.

[2].O'zbekiston Respublikasining "Suv va suvdan foydalanish to'g'risida"gi Qonuni, 1993. www.lex.uz-O'z.P Qonun hujjatlari ma'lumotlari milliy bazasi.

[3]. Abdullaev T.A. «Ochiq suv manbalaridan suv oluvchi inshootlarni loyihalash» o'quv qo'llanma. Toshkent 1997. <http://www.ziyo.net.uz>

[4] S.D.Nurmurodov, A.XRasulov, K.G. Baxadirov. Materialshunoslik va konstruksion materiallar texnologiyasi. – Namangan, 2024. – B. <http://www.Valtec.ru>

[5] Qoshmurodov A., Umarov A., Ziyayeva P. Mineralogiya. – Toshkent, 2020. – B. <http://www.Vent.ru>

[6] Q.Saydullayev, K.Shukurova. Metall konstruksiyalari (darslik). – NamDU, 2024. – B. <http://www.energ.narod.ru>

[7] Rashidov Yu.K., Koroli M.A. “Isitish”. O‘quv qo‘llanma 2000 yil. 96b. <http://www.Vent.ru>

[8] Tursunova U.X., Mamajonov T.M. “Issiqlik ta’minoti”. O‘quv qo‘llanma, Toshkent, Talkin, 2004 y. 126 b. <http://www.energ.narod.ru>

[9] S.R.Saydullayev “Binolarning injinerlik kommunikatsiyalari” darslik Toshkent 2021 yil <http://www.Vent.ru>

[10] S.R.Saydullayev. "Issiqlik ta'minoti tizimlari (Issiqlik ta'minoti va issiqlik jarayonlari)". O‘quv qo‘llanma - 2021-Toshkent. 205 bet. <http://www.Vent.ru>

[11] “ O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Qurilish va uy-joy kommunal xo‘jaligi vazirligi”. Muhandislik tizimlari bo‘yicha texnik reglamentlar to‘plami, Toshkent, 2023. <http://www.energ.narod.ru>

[12] Karimov A. R., “Zamonaviy qurilish materiallari va ularning xossalari”, TATU nashriyoti, 2022. <http://www.Vent.ru>

[13] ISO 14001:2020 – “Environmental management systems — Requirements with guidance for use” <http://www.Vent.ru>

[14] Rahimov S. B., “Muhandislik tizimlarini loyihalashda innovatsion yondashuvlar”, “Qurilish muhandisi” jurnali, 2024, №2. <http://www.ziyo.net.uz>

[15]. European Committee for Standardization (CEN). “EN 1057:2018 Copper and copper alloys — Seamless, round copper tubes for water and gas in sanitary and heating applications.” <http://www.ziyo.net.uz>

[16] ISO 14001:2020 – “Environmental management systems — Requirements with guidance for use” <http://www.Vent.ru>